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WRITTEN LANGUAGE IN THE FACE OF COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES: ITS IMPACT AVA-MOODLE AT IFSUDESTEMG - SÃO JOÃO DEL REY - BRAZIL

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ABSTRACT

With the popularization of the Internet, there has been an increase in the number of mobile devices and, as a result, the development of computer tools. The use of computational tools in virtual learning environments allows for numerous teaching-supported experiences. This work highlights pedagogical aspects in the development of teacher writing in a virtual learning environment - Moodle. It analyzes the use of information and communication technology (ICT) by teachers and students in virtual learning environments. It aims to identify teachers' writing through a quantitative and qualitative study to investigate the influence on students' writing patterns of the use of formal language to the detriment of digital language, "internetese", supported by the use of synchronous and asynchronous tools. The study proves that teenagers not only know how to distinguish which computer tool they are on, but also behave according to the formality of a forum or the informality of a chat.